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Review on Regional Standardized Training of First-year Teachers in Shanghai

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Abstract

Shanghai has promoted regional induction for first-year teachers since 2012. In Mar 2012, Shanghai Municipal education commission (SMEC) issued "Guidance of regional standardized training of first-year teachers in Shanghai"(RSTFTS). According to this guidance first-year teachers are required of 1-year induction after recruitment. As training content should consist of four parts, namely, professional perception and teacher ethics cultivation, classroom experience and teaching practice, class management and ethics experience, fieldwork and professional development. Regional Education Bureau (REB), Regional Teachers' Education College (RTEC), kindergartens, primary and secondary schools (K-12 schools) of Shanghai's 16 districts have participated in this program. All 15 districts and 1 country in Shanghai have followed the guideline and taken charge in specific training affairs, which finally accumulated rich experiences in 7 years.

Keywords: Teacher Induction, First-Year Teacher, Teachers' Professional Development (TPD), Regional Standardized Training of First-year Teachers, Shanghai

1. Introduction

1.1 Teacher Induction in Contemporary China

Informal teacher induction (ITI) has a long history in school field, mainly organized by school administrators. Most ITI constitutes of being assigned to an experienced teacher, participates in classroom observation, as well as involved in subject group and teamwork. Usually informal teacher induction (ITI) is not required by school districts. Though ITI is under the charge of specific school, most school even doesn't have definite requirement. ITI is conducted inside of subject teaching group. For example, new English teacher would like to watch how senior English teachers teach in the same context. The purpose of ITI is to help new teacher to adapt to campus, facilities, and school table, communicate with colleagues, and get familiar with subject matter knowledge and so on. New teachers frequently meet difficulties and frustration in daily practice, as well as feel confused in playing teachers' occupation role (Qu, 1990; Liu, 1996; Ye, 1998; Gu, 1999; Ren, 2004; Chen, 2008).

In 1952, Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China held an administrative meeting on primary and secondary education, which discussed how to strengthen in-service training of primary and secondary school teachers. This meeting finally decided to establish teachers' training system, which aimed at improving teachers' political, cultural and professional literacy. In September 1952, Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China issued a circular on the issue of primary and secondary school teachers further education. It was suggested that teachers' training colleges, correspondence normal schools and teachers' part-time schools should be set up everywhere in order to strengthen teachers' in-service education (MEPRC, 1952). In 1953, Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China and the Ministry of Finance of the People's Republic of China jointed together and made some supplementary provisions to guarantee in-service training of teachers (MEPRC, 1953). During the Cultural Revolution (1966-1976), teachers' training colleges and normal universities were merged or stopped. Regional in-service training for primary and secondary school teachers also stagnated from 1968 to 1978.

In December 1978, the Third Plenary Session of the Tenth Central Committee was convened. Normal education and teachers' in-service training started to get back on the right track. In 1980, Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China issued "Opinions on Strengthening the Further Training of in-service Teachers in Primary and Secondary Schools". The Opinions put forward: "The government should combine the systematic study on knowledge of teacher professional development, and strengthen the teachers' work" (MEPRC, 1980). From the late 1970s to the 1990s, normal universities and colleges, College of Continuing Education, as well as teachers' training colleges jointed together to undertake and support teachers' training. Teachers' education colleges trained primary school teachers who did not have the diploma of secondary normal colleges. In 1980, "the Consultation Report of Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China on Several Questions of Normal Education" clearly pointed out that we should make contributions to the practice of basic education (MEPRC, 1980). In order to clarify the tasks, scope and principles of teachers' training in primary and secondary schools, in March 1986, Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China (MEPRC) issued the "Plan and Opinions on Basic Education Teachers and normal Education". And in April 1986, the "Compulsory Education Law" stipulated that "the State should develop and accelerate teacher education" (MEPRC, 1986). In China, there was 1-year probation system existed for new teachers. The Teachers' Law of the People's Republic of China also clearly stipulated that "after obtaining professional qualification and get offer as a new teacher, he or she would have 1-year probation." However, new teacher's probation system in China mainly focused on the difference of personnel salary. At the end of 1 years' probation, after passing professional test, the newly appointed teachers will get the same salary as formal teachers. Since the 1990s, with the emphasis on teachers' continuing education, the first year of probation training for new teachers had gradually been put on administrations' agenda. In September 1999, the "Stipulation for Continuing Education in Primary and Secondary Schools" implemented that "Continuing Education for Primary and Secondary School Teachers includes non-diploma education and diploma education". According to this regulation, non-diploma education includes professional training, which should be arranged of no less than 120 hours of training session for new teachers during the probation period" (MEPRC, 1999).

On Sep 1999, Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China promulgated "the Provisions on Continuing Education for Primary and Secondary School Teachers", which stated: "Continuing Education for Primary and Secondary School Teachers is divided into non-diploma education and diploma education. Non-diploma education includes the training of new teachers, which is set up for new teachers to meet the needs of education and teaching during the probation period. "Teachers' continuing education colleges at all levels and normal universities carried out continuing education for primary and secondary school teachers. Primary and secondary schools were required to assure teachers participating in continuing education, as well as organize various forms of training in local school (MEPRC, 1999). In March 2002, Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China issued "the Opinions on the Reform and Development of Teacher Education during the Tenth Five-Year Plan Period", which affirmed that there had been a breakthrough in the construction of professional training for primary and secondary school teachers during the Ninth Five-Year Plan Period (MEPRC, 2002). The project of continuing education for primary and secondary school teachers has been implemented overall. And teachers' continuing education colleges at all levels have mainly carried out information technology training and professional ethics training in various forms. Based on the "Provisions for Continuing Education of Primary and Secondary School Teachers", a great deal of national, provincial and municipal level training for key teachers emerged. The report "Opinions on the

Reform and Development of Teacher Education during the Tenth Five-Year Plan" clearly pointed out: "Continually strengthen the construction of regional teachers training colleges and institutions. All provinces including autonomous regions and municipalities directly under the Central Government must establish teachers training centres"(MEPRC, 2002).

In 2011, Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China promulgated the Opinions on Strengthening the Training of Primary and Secondary School Teachers, which positioned the overall requirements for the training of primary and secondary school teachers in the new period: "All of district and county teacher training institutions should fully play the role of service and support. Local Government should promote the integration of regional teachers' further education schools with relevant institutions, strengthen the basic capacity building of teacher training institutions at County level, promote the integration of learning and training resources from universities and colleges to primary and secondary schools, as well as form regional teacher's learning and resource centers. Those regional learning and resource centers should coordinate centralized training, distance training as well as support school-based research. All new teachers should attend not less than 120 hours pre-service training in order to adapt to education and teaching as soon as possible (MEPRC, 2011).

1.2 Regional Standardized Training of First-year Teachers: Shanghai's Exploration and Innovation

In 2010 "National Medium & Long-Term Education Reform and Development Plan of China (2010-2020)" suggested that the national country to improve teacher's management system, set teachers' qualification standards, strictly implement the teachers' admission system and control the professional entrance of teachers. The state has established teacher qualification standards of academic and morality requirements. The state will establish a regular registration system for teachers' qualification certificates. The provincial education administration uniformly organizes the literacy examination and professional certification for primary and secondary school teachers. And national administration plays important role in recruitment of primary and secondary school teachers, application of professional title, training and assessment (MEPRC, 2010).

Since newly recruited teachers' education backgrounds are different. The professional theoretical knowledge acquired by newly recruited teachers during their higher education often has hysteresis when they finally get the offer. Newly recruited teachers frequently feel difficult to adapt to the teacher's role and the teaching positions' requirements at the very beginning. Therefore, it is necessary to provide induction for first-year teacher and complete the role transition from student teacher to formal teacher.

In response to the call for the National Medium & Long-Term Education Reform and Development Plan (2010-2020). In 2012 Shanghai Municipal Education Commission promulgated the "Guidance on regional standardized training of first-year teachers in Primary and Secondary Schools (Kindergarten) (Trial)" (hereinafter referred to as "Guidance"), which indicated the implementation of first-year teachers' induction in Shanghai.

Educational Administration coordinates city's training resources as well as regional training resources. First-Year Teacher; will be placed in teaching community, instructed by mentors, correctly understand and adapt to the role of teachers, strengthen the teaching ability, and finally become competent for teaching. On April 11, 2012, the Shanghai regional standardized training of first-year teachers in Primary and Secondary Schools (Kindergarten) Launch Conference was held in Shanghai Jinyuan High School, which marked the inauguration of formal teacher induction.

According to "Guidance on regional standardized training of first-year teachers in Primary and Secondary Schools (Kindergarten) ", teacher professional development school (TPDS) would be assigned in municipal level and district level. Regional standardized training of first-year teachers in Primary and Secondary Schools (Kindergarten) would be organized by teacher professional development school (TPDS) and appointment school which has recruited new teachers. Shanghai Municipal Education Commission invited experts to carry out annual review on teacher professional development school (TPDS). Passing annual review, teacher professional development school (TPDS) would get the next year's certification (SMEC, 2012).

"Guidance on regional standardized training of first-year teachers in Primary and Secondary Schools (Kindergarten)" has 1300 characters. This guidance responds to "the National Medium & Long-Term Education Reform and Development Plan (2010-2020)", and aims at improving and strictly implementing the teacher's admission system. The guidance requires first-year teachers to participate in teacher induction during first-year. The training content is composed of four parts, namely, professional perception and teacher ethics cultivation, classroom experience and teaching practice, classroom management and moral education, teaching research and professional development. First-year teachers should complete teacher induction within one year, basically grasp the key points of the training contents in the four major sectors, meet the corresponding standards and requirements, so as to obtain the qualifications of teachers' posts (SMEC, 2012).

Since 2012, Shanghai's basic education system has implemented standardized training system for first-year teachers. Graduates from normal universities and colleges are scheduled to participate in unified content and standard training in teachers' professional development schools during the first-year induction period (SMEC, 2012).

Establish training base to improve training ability. Shanghai has selected a few schools with advanced concepts and outstanding achievements in promoting professional development of teachers, training first-year teachers and guiding the practice of student teachers. Teacher professional development school should play a demonstration, radiation and leading role for neighborhood schools. As the first batch of training bases to carry out exploratory pilot projects, these selected training base schools continue to practice, innovative methods, and actively undertake the dual task of training first-year teachers. In order to ensure the training quality of training base schools, the Municipal Education Commission has also established the mechanism of declaration, evaluation, access and annual inspection of training base schools (SMEC, 2012).

Design content scientifically and define training objectives. The standardized training of Probationary Teachers is the content that new teachers should know when they first take up their posts, such as preparing lessons, classes, designing assignments, preparing examinations, evaluating students, teaching and research activities, student interviews, home visits, class teacher's work, guidance of community activities, offering elective courses, other part-time jobs in schools, etc. It covers professional awareness. There are eighteen key points in four aspects: professional perception and teacher ethics cultivation, classroom experience and teaching practice, classroom management and moral education, teaching research and professional development. Each key point has specific objectives, training methods, accomplish process and outcome records (SMEC, 2012).

Establish supporting policies to ensure the implementation of training. During the standardized training period, first-year teachers will sign employment contracts with institutions appointed by schools or regional education bureaus, and enjoy the same treatment as in-service teachers. After the training, the contract will be terminated naturally, and the assessment will be completed jointly by the regional teachers' education college, training schools' bases, and appointment schools which have enrolled first-year teachers (SMEC, 2012).

Develop pilot training and explore training mode. From September 2011 to July 2012, Shanghai selected four districts, concluding Xuhui, Changning, Putuo and Fengxian, to conduct internship training for first-year teachers. 570 first-year teachers participated in the training. The Shanghai Municipal Education Commission has set up an expert guidance group to equip each pilot area with six experts from basic education field. Experts visit each training school base once a month for guidance. Experts will spend no less than half a day each time on fully understanding the training process, helping regional education bureau, training school bases and instructors to sum up experience, pointing out existing problems, and giving suggestions. According to training school's own conditions, characteristics and the law of teachers' professional growth, the pilot schools have creatively carried out training and achieved experience (SMEC, 2012).

2. Municipal Construction of Standardized Training of First-year Teachers in Shanghai

2.1 Ideological Guidance

Guided by the professional standards of primary and secondary school teachers, we should improve and strictly implement the teacher admission system, strictly control the entrance of teachers, consolidate the professional foundation of first-year teachers, and improve the quality and ability of first-year teachers in P district. Studying the professional needs and growth rules of first-year teachers, coordinating and coordinating high-quality educational resources at district and school levels, so that first-year teachers can correctly recognize and quickly adapt to the role of teachers in the infiltration of excellent educational and teaching teams and in the process of teaching by specialized instructors, form good norms of educational and teaching behavior, and strengthen education and teaching. Practice ability and be competent for education and teaching as soon as possible (Yu & Wu, 2015).

2.2 Training Objects and Targets

Graduates from normal universities or other institutions of higher education in that year and taught in primary and secondary schools, kindergartens and vocational schools, but have not obtained the "Shanghai First-year teachers' Standardized Training Certification" Graduates and social workers who first serve in primary and secondary schools, kindergartens and vocational schools, are required to attend teacher induction during their first-year's employment (Shanghai Beginning Teachers' Standardization Training Project Group, 2014).

"Guidance on regional standardized training of first-year teachers in Primary and Secondary Schools (Kindergarten)" requires first-year teachers to participate in teacher induction during first-year. The training content is composed of four parts, namely, professional perception and teacher ethics cultivation, classroom experience and teaching practice, classroom management and moral education, teaching research and professional development. First-year teachers should complete teacher induction within one year, basically grasp the key points of the training contents in the four major sectors, meet the corresponding standards and requirements, so as to obtain the qualifications of teachers' posts (SMEC, 2012).

Regional standardized training of first-year teachers in Primary and Secondary Schools (Kindergarten) would be organized by teacher professional development school (TPDS) and servicing school which has recruited new teachers. Shanghai Municipal Education Commission invited experts to carry out annual review on teacher professional development school (TPDS). Passing annual review, teacher professional development school (TPDS) would get the next year's certification (SMEC, 2012).

2.3 Organization Frame of Standardized Training of First-year Teachers in Shanghai

Standardized training of first-year teachers in Shanghai is conducted at municipal level, while at the same time is operated and designed in details at regional level (Chen&An, 2016).

Table 1 Organization Frame of Standardized Training of First-year Teachers in Shanghai

Organization Frame of Standardized Training of First-year Teachers in Shanghai		
Roles	Municipal level	Regional Level
Educational Administer	Shanghai Municipal Education Commission	Regional Education Bureau
Organizers and Host	Shanghai Teacher Training Center	Regional Teacher's Training College
Cooperation Unit	Teachers' Professional Development School Training School (train new teacher)	Appointment school (recruit new teacher)

2.4 Organization Frame of Standardized Training of First-year Teachers in Shanghai

First-year teachers initialize "Trainee-Manual" to fill in blank forms and record training content. Mentors gave formative assessment and comments during fixed time session (Xia, 2018).

Table 2 Organization Frame of Standardized Training of First-year Teachers in Shanghai

Organization Frame of Standardized Training of First-year Teachers in Shanghai	
Training Section	Training Content
Professional Perception and Teacher Ethics Cultivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -First-year teachers draw up individual training plan with instructors. -Read a book about teachers' career development or morality and write reading notes. -Write ten informal essays on teachers' career experience during the training period. -Finish personal summary.
Classroom Experience and Teaching Practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Study subject course standard, make relative speech and write down outline. -Analysis unit teaching material, complete teaching plan, practice writing on the blackboard, as well as present teaching plan. -Complete the conception and syllabus of an extended elective course and try to teach an elective course. -Watch on 10 lessons and write down classroom observation report. -Three Formal Trials on subject teaching. -Watch and comment on three other teachers' lessons. -Design a unit of student assignments and interpret the reasons. -Design unit exams, make quality analysis after the actual test, complete mid-term and final exam class quality analysis.
Classroom Management and Moral Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Hold on a student leader meeting, a student symposium, and promote home visit for some student's specific problem. -Plan and host a class meeting, organize one social activity and practice. -Write a class situation analysis and two students' case analysis. -Write the phrase of comprehensive evaluation of students' semester.
Field work and Professional Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Intensive reading of professional books recommended by tutors. -Conclude reading notes, and carry out self-study of relevant books. -Participate in teaching and research group activities and undertake relevant tasks. Plan and host a lesson preparation group activity. -Three-year Personal Professional Development Plan
Others	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Instruction Agreement -Evaluation of Training Center
Appendix	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Hard-pen Calligraphy (at the beginning of training) -Hard-pen Calligraphy (after the training) -Utilize and design teaching aids and courseware

2.5 Regional Training Mode

Shanghai Municipal education commission takes charge of overall design of regional standardized training of first-year teachers. Regional Education Bureau and regional teacher training college conduct and supervise regional standardized training of first-year teachers. Teacher professional development school (training school) and appointment school undertake regional standardized training of first-year teachers. Regional standardized training of first-year teachers generally has 4 sections (Xu et al., 2018).

Table 3 Regional Training Mode

Regional training mode			
Section	Organizer	Theme & Content	Mode
Orientation	Regional Education College	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Program introduction -Career counseling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Lecture -Workshop
Centralized training	Regional Education College	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Subject teaching -Classroom management -Moral education -Education research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Lecture -Group work -Demonstration course -On-line training
In-service training	Teacher development school (Training school)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Subject teaching -Classroom management -Moral education -Education research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Group work -Class observation -Teaching activities -Open Courses
	Appointment school	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Subject teaching 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Demonstration course

		-Classroom management -Moral education -Education research	-Training & Practice
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3. Regional practice of standardized training of first-year teachers in Shanghai

3.1 Regional Training Object

P district has built a number of standardized training courses, which are guided by teachers' professional development standards, based on training needs, closed to the reality of first-year teachers, and finally accelerate their professional development. It constructs standardized training curriculum system for first-year teachers according to the regional education situation rebuilds original training courses for first-year teachers, and finally improve the quality and efficiency of first-year teachers.

Y district lies in the northeast of shanghai city. It holds standardized training of first-year teachers in whole area aims to: "Make full use of high-quality education resources in whole region, consolidate the professional foundation of the first-year teachers, improve the professional quality of regional first-year teachers, organize and carry out the training of first-year teachers at higher point, higher standard and higher level. Excellent teaching groups and experts will participate in instructing teaching process. First-year teachers should form good norms of education and teaching behavior, strengthen practical ability of teaching, and be competent for the post as soon as possible."Standardized Training Scheme for kindergarten, primary and secondary school's first-year teachers of Y district in 2012" is applicable to graduates from normal universities or other higher institutions, and those who first teach in primary and secondary schools, kindergartens, vocational schools, Children's Palace, Youth Science and Technology Station.

3.2 Regional Curriculum Framework

Since the implementation of standardized training for first-year teachers, P district has always regarded the development of standardized training courses for first-year teachers as an important task, which has been strictly planned. After several rounds of practice of standardized training of first-year teachers, training base schools closely link school-based induction content to the requirements of guidance, which has initially formed some standardized training courses for first-year teachers in line with the regional's actual situation (Institute of Education Development in P district, 2014). So far, P district has constructed 3-level curriculum system for standardized training of first-year teachers as follows:

Figure 1 3-level curriculum system for standardized training of first-year teachers in P district

Curriculum system for standardized training of first-year teachers in Y district is conducted from 4 levels: regional level, school level, teaching group level, and individual level.

Table 4 Curriculum structure for standardized training of first-year teachers in Y district

Curriculum system for standardized training of first-year teachers in Y district	
Morality and Literacy	-Educational theory -Moral sentiment -Humanistic literacy -Scientific literacy -Mental health care -Educational art
Knowledge and Skill	-Educational concept -Subject knowledge -Teaching skills -Curriculum development -Class management -Scientific research method -Innovation ability -Moral education -Psychological techniques -Information Technology
Practice and Experience	-Case analysis -Curriculum construction -Teaching method -Educational research -Class management -Group construction

Table 5 Curriculum system for standardized training of first-year teachers in Y district

Curriculum structure for standardized training of first-year teachers in Y district					
Level	Session	Objectives	Modular	Methods	Faculty
Region Level	K-12	-Professional accomplishment -Teachers' Morality and Literacy -Teaching Knowledge and Practice -Students' Psychology	-Morality and - Literacy -Knowledge and Skill -Practice & Action	-Lecture -Group work -Field work -Online training -Elective units	-Experts -Subject research fellow -Excellent teacher
School Level	K-12	-Pedagogical Content Knowledge -Content Knowledge - Professional identity	-Culture Adaption -Campus Culture -School-based Curriculum	-Group work -Classroom - Observation	-School administrator -Excellent teacher

		-Teaching Knowledge and Skills			
Teaching Group	K-12	-Team Work -Teaching Content and - Technology	-Subject knowledge -Discipline activities -Practice &Skills	-Group work -Classroom Observation -Learning Community	-Experienced teacher
Subject Level	1-12	-Teachers' role and duty -Teaching Content and Technology	-PCK -Daily-Practice -Teaching Strategy	-Group work -Classroom Observation -Learning Community Peer work	-Experienced teacher
Head Teacher	1-12	-Students' Psychology -Theory and Practice -Classroom Management	-Daily Affairs -Knowledge and Skill	-Thematic counseling -Individualized Tutor -1 to 1mentor	-Experienced teacher
Nursery	K	-Child Psychology (3-6years old) -Nursery Theory -Games and Activities -Preschool education theory	-Daily practice -Nursing Strategy	-Thematic counseling	-Experienced teacher
Daily Management	K	-Classroom Management -Child Psychology (3-6years old)	-Daily practice -Management strategy	-Thematic counseling -Individualized Tutor -1 to 1mentor	-Experienced teacher

3.3 Regional Curriculum Requirements

Besides municipal's requirements, regional curriculum requirements of standardized training of first-year teachers in P district covers : content requirements, format requirements , training hours and implementation requirements, training hours and implementation requirements.

Table 6 Curriculum Requirements of standardized training of first-year teachers in P district

Regional Curriculum Requirements of Standardized Training of First-year Teachers in P district (2014)	
Content Requirements	-Embody the advanced nature -Highlighting practicality -Emphasize innovation -Focus on development
Format Requirements	-Course category: General Studies Course, Professional Courses -The course materials submitted in the application mainly include the following contents: the course's title, school section and subject suitable for, lecturer's qualification, the analysis of the training objects and needs, the background and significance of the course, the course contents with three-level outline, the main characteristics and innovation of the course, the arrangement of the class hours, the course implementation process and mode, and course evaluation, etc. Specifically, it refers to the Information Table for Collection and Application of Standardized Training Courses for first-year teachers in P district.
Implementation Requirements	-Class hours: 5 to 20 hours; 1-4 half-day, 5 hours in each half-day (inside the district); 1-4 half-day, 4 hours in each half-day (outside the district). -The implementation of the curriculum should be comprehensive in many forms, including: lecture (highlighting case teaching, supplemented by observation, interactive discussion, etc.), discussion (student activities, observation and diagnosis), as well as network platform (watch micro-video, participate in forum interaction etc.).

Faculty Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Recommendation: single school or school alliance -Declaration: single teacher or teaching group -Applicant Qualifications: curriculum director should have rich training experience, teaching and moral management experience, distinct training characteristics and remarkable training effect. Generally, curriculum applicant should have middle or senior professional titles or has already become regional discipline leader or key teacher.
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3.4 Procedures of Regional Curriculum Construction

The construction of standardized training curriculum for first-year teachers in P district adopts the dynamic management mode of fair competition, selection of the best, process management, continuing development, project establishment and under co-construction of schools and districts. The following procedures generally concluded: announcement, declaration, submission, review, and evaluation.

Table 7 Procedures of Regional Curriculum Construction in P district

Procedures of Regional Curriculum Construction in P district	
Announcement	-Regional Education Bureau and Regional teachers' training college organize curriculum construction, formulate procedure, and post announcement in district.
Declaration	-Teachers declare independently. Schools advance first-selection inside campus and recommend high-quality courses. Teachers submit curriculum application material to school.
Submission	-Schools submit teachers' curriculum application material to regional education bureau and regional teachers' training college.
Review	-Regional education bureau and regional teachers' training college invite experts to review curriculum under selection. Experts recommend curriculum list for further selection.
Results	-Regional education bureau publish selected courses and support curriculum construction.
Curriculum Cultivation	-Experts give guidance and advice on curriculum cultivation. Declared teachers follow experts' guidance, further improve the curriculum structure, content and form, write or revise textbooks, record video course and finally public online.
Evaluation	-Regional Education Bureau and Regional teachers' training college organize formative evaluation and summative evaluation on curriculum construction and curriculum application. Curriculum's audience and attendant participate in evaluation. Experts conduct declaration review, term review, and annual review on curriculum.
Application & Promotion	-Curriculums which have passed declaration review will be divided into 2 categories concluding "excellent" and "qualified". "Excellent" and "qualified" curriculums will be selected in district-level training courses, and participate in term review and annual review successively. Curriculums achieved excellent title will be popularized and spread in district and recommend to municipal level.

Regional education bureau and regional teacher education school in P district formulate mentor's package, as well as provide mentors with guidance and task information.

Table 8 Catalog of Mentor's Package in P district

Catalog of Mentor's Package in P district	
Personal Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Basic information of subject mentor -Basic information of first-year teachers (Mentee)
Plan & Summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Mentor's Work Plan -Mentor's personal summary
Records of Instruction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Records of class attendance -Records of First-year teachers' Preparations for Lessons (SemesterI/II) -Records of First-year teachers' Homework Arrangement (SemesterI/II) -Records of First-year teachers' Open Class Attendance (SemesterI/II)
Evaluation	-School's evaluation of mentor

	-Regional evaluation and commendation of mentor
	-Municipal commendation of mentor

Inside this package, education administrators' analysis duties of subject mentors, as well as duties of head teacher's tutor.

Table 9 Duties of Subject Mentors in P district

Duties of Subject Mentors in P district	
General Qualifications	-Familiar with the contents and requirements of the standardized training of teachers in P district, and pay attention to the full growth of first-year teachers. -Mentors should set an example and influence the First-Year Teacher; imperceptibly show their excellent teachers' moral cultivation and etiquette norms.
Mentor's Assignment	-Mentors should initiatively introduce to First-Year Teacher; of the school's history, characteristics campus and culture, so that the first-year teachers can know the school, accept the school and identify with the school. -Mentors should guide First-Year Teacher; to obtain basic skills in subject teaching and help them to form good teaching habits. -Check the contents of "Pudong New District Primary and Secondary Schools (Kindergartens) Standardized Training Manual for First-year teachers" filled out by first-year teachers in time, and provide relevant evaluation seriously. -Fill in the blanks of mentor' package in time, and complete the assignment of instructor.
Mentor's Responsibility	-Accept the training, guidance, assessment of the mentor's work by the school and district.

Table 10 Duties of Head Teacher's Tutor in P district

Duties of Head Teacher's Tutor in P district	
General Qualifications	-10 years of working experience as a head teacher or an education administrator in school. -District academic leader and key teacher.
Tutor's Assignment	-Tutor should instruct head teacher to promote and conduct: *Class Cadre Meeting *Home visit *Student Symposium *Home-school contact *Class Meeting *Class Social Practice Activities *Class Situation Analysis *Student Case Analysis *Comprehensive Evaluation of Students -Fill in the blanks of tutor' package in time, and complete the assignment of instructor.
Tutor's Responsibility	-Accept the training, guidance, assessment of the tutor's work by the school and district.

4. Conclusion

In the past, China's probation system was mainly from the perspective of personnel wages. Upon the expiration of one-year probation period, the first-year teacher will be transferred to regular rank after passing the examination, and will receive the salary as formal teachers. In practice, in the probation period, the traditional apprentice guidance is basically limited to the small scope of the school, that is, the school arranges the mentor to guide first-year teachers, so as to continue the previous independent support between schools. After the national medium and long term education reform and development plan (2010-2020) issued in 2010, it was pointed out that the strategic requirements of "improving and strictly implementing the teacher access system and strict the entrance of teachers". New mechanisms of national standard, provincial examination, county recruitment and district policy should be piloted to further improve the enrollment standard for new teachers. This paper attempts to integrate and link the

teacher's induction and the current one-year probation system into the terms of "teachers' rights and obligations" in the new round of education program revision. In the supplement to the provisions on the continuing education of primary and secondary school teachers, it is confirmed that the first-year teachers must participate in induction during the current one-year probation period, and they can get formal offer after passing the training.

China has a vast territory and complicated regional characteristics. Simply unified national teacher induction is not operational, so the province and city should try to gradually implement the teacher's in-service training system including teacher induction. In 2012, Shanghai carried out the standardized training of first-year teachers, and provided one-year probationary training for new teachers in regional teachers' colleges and teachers' professional development schools of the counties. The training contents covered four major parts and 18 key points, including professional perception and moral cultivation, classroom experience and teaching practice, classroom management and moral experience, teaching research and professional development. Forming three level collaborative operation mode engaged cities, districts and schools which adopts team teaching, equipped with discipline teaching and head teacher teaching, bringing new teachers into teaching, moral and research teams, constructing school and district learning communities, and providing all-round guidance.

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